

REVIEW: LAZĂR VLĂSCLEANU - EDUCATION AND POWER, POLIROM PUBLISHING HOUSE, IAȘI, 2020

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The Polirom Publishing House in Iași confirms once again the important role it plays in the promotion of quality Romanian pedagogical literature, by publishing the work of the Bucharest professor Lazăr Vlăsceanu *Education and Power*.

The sociology-anthropology collection within the Polirom, coordinated by the same Lazăr Vlăsceanu, together with Liviu Cernea, proposes a much-needed interdisciplinary approach, realized this time through an analysis of education from a sociological and political perspective.

The main title of the work suggests a direct analysis of two important sectors of social life: education and power. Power can be understood as a core of social activities. Near it is the political life (confrontation between the parties), the legal and administrative institutions (the police and the army have an essential role). Economy, finance are also not far away, while culture and education are usually at a greater distance, if not at the antipodes.

As early as 1975, Paul Henry Chambat de Lauwe captured in the volume *La culture et le pouvoir* concrete determinations between these two social domains, revealing the complex functions of innovative and self-educational culture.

In an even more explicit manner, Michel Apple revealed the incidence of curriculum, especially curriculum in the substance of the social-political network (see *Education and Power*).

The first two parts of Vlăsceanu's book, the first denoting the *opening* and the second *transformation* aim at distinct planes. The first plan refers to the social-political state of Romanian education, the paradox between the politician's statements regarding the priority of education in the whole of social life, on the one hand, and the modest financing of education, on the other hand, which explains the "precarious state of our education", the finding gloomy that "a lot, a lot of information is converging in one direction. The average level of individual education has fallen below the threshold of any decent acceptability, if we compare ourselves with ourselves before 1990, or with other Europeans after 2000" (Vlăsceanu Lazar, *Education and power*, Polirom Publishing House, Iași, 2020, page 11).

The virulently critical attitude towards Romanian education is reminiscent of Ioan Negreț Dobridor's book, whose title *Pedagogical Catastrophe* is as significant as possible.

The fact that Romania allocates the lowest percentage of GDP to education, 3-3.5% compared to the EU average of almost 5%, reveals, of course, an intolerable strategy. When we analyze this situation, we must also take into account the sphere of the economy and especially of culture, informal education, represented by the very large sector of private consultations (meditations for the

baccalaureate in mathematics and physics, informal counseling, for the development of bachelor's theses, master's, PhD, etc.).

We do not entirely share the distinguished professor's vision regarding the future of the Romanian people. Although it is sensitive to economic and financial conditions, education is characterized by a high potential for resilience, especially for our people, who have withstood so many vicissitudes, not only cultural, but especially social-political and economic. Without giving in too many details, but we only remember Mateevici's wonderful verse "our language is a treasure".

Indeed, a connoisseur of the Romanian language, can understand and accept Western culture more easily. Millions of Romanians, by virtue of very limited resources, preferred to emigrate to France, Spain and especially to Italy.

Romanian education and culture can feel Western culture much more easily and will be able to adopt the standards of civilization more quickly.

The second part of Vlăsceanu's book, *Transformation* contains an excellent analysis pertinent to the four levels of education: from early childhood, primary, secondary education and the last level, higher education. Useful, meaningful, interesting information at the highest level is generously offered, of interest not only to specialists in sociology, education, teachers, but also to the general public.